

Entangled states induced by electron-phonon interaction in two dimensional materials

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(Dated: July 11, 2025)

ABSTRACT

We report on the effects of electron-phonon interaction in materials like graphene, showing that it enables the formation of a gap bridged by unique edge states. These states exhibit a distinctive locking between propagation direction, valley, and phonon mode, allowing for the generation of electron-phonon entangled states whose parts can be easily split. We discuss the effect of the chiral atomic motion in the zone-boundary phonons leading to this effect. Our findings shed light on how to harness these unconventional states in quantum research.

Keywords: Entangled states, electron-phonon interaction, two-dimensional materials

Introduction.— Chiral effects for electrons are prevalent in condensed matter physics, and especially in quantum materials [1] influencing phenomena ranging from the integer quantum Hall effect [2] and the quantum spin Hall effect [3, 4], to the chiral behavior associated with different valleys in graphene [5–7]. Despite the abundance of electron chiral effects, the exploration of phonon chirality has only gained traction recently. This development was motivated by the proposal [8] and subsequent observation of chiral phonons in tungsten diselenide (WSe₂) [9], a two-dimensional material with broken inversion symmetry.

Chiral phonons, which are collective oscillations of a crystal lattice, exhibit a definitive handedness [10], setting them apart from traditional textbook examples which correspond to achiral modes [11–13]. Although the non-zero total pseudoangular momentum (PAM) is enabled by inversion symmetry breaking in two dimensional materials, the chiral motion of sublattices is present even preserving this symmetry. The burgeoning interest in this collective chiral motion of the atoms has positioned them at the epicenter of an incipient but expanding research frontier [14–20]. Given the long history of remarkable effects arising due to electron-phonon interactions [21–27], a natural question is whether the chirality of phonons may impart remarkable effects on electrons via their interaction. Previous studies have suggested that the interaction with one zone boundary mode with chiral displacement of the atoms can induce co-propagating edge states [28], and that chiral phonons may incite unconventional and high-temperature superconductivity [29].

Here we unravel a different aspect of this puzzle showing how electron-phonon interaction can lead to a gap bridged by electron-phonon entangled states. Using a non-adiabatic and non-perturbative framework we consider the interaction between electrons and two zone-boundary phonon modes, re-

lated by time-reversal symmetry. In these modes, the atoms on each sublattice describe a chiral motion. We demonstrate how selective *Umklapp* processes, linking each of the two modes with the electrons in distinct valleys, give rise to a gap with counter-propagating edge states. These edge states display a locking between the propagation direction, the valley, and the excited phonon mode. As pointed out in [30], while in solid state physics entangling is natural, as most interactions tend to generate entangled states, separating them in a useful way is challenging. The opposite occurs in optics, where splitting the entangled parts can be easily achieved through a beam splitter [31], but entangling the states is the challenge. In the case presented here, the locking among propagation-direction, valley and marker-state allows for a simple way to achieve both the entanglement and the splitting of the state in potentially useful ways. Imagine an electron entering a sample with such characteristics at a T-junction; it would bifurcate and propagate along the edge in two opposite directions. Measuring the phonon number would then collapse the state into one of two possible outcomes. Additionally, we propose a simulated experiment designed provide evidence of this entanglement as a suppression of interference in a *which path* interferometric setup.

Hamiltonian Model.— We start with a nearest neighbor Hamiltonian for electrons in a honeycomb lattice:

$$\mathcal{H}_e = \sum_n \Delta_n c_n^\dagger c_n - \sum_{\langle n,m \rangle} \gamma_{n,m} c_n^\dagger c_m, \quad (1)$$

where c_n is the annihilation operator for electrons at site n , and the second sum on the right hand side runs over nearest neighbors which are connected by the hopping term $\gamma_{n,m}$. The onsite energies Δ_n take the values Δ or $-\Delta$, depending on the sublattice (A or B), so as to model a staggering potential.

The atomic displacements produced by a phonon mode with wave-vector \mathbf{G} and angular frequency ω can be written as $\delta \mathbf{r}_{\ell,\alpha}(t) = \text{Re}[A_{\mathbf{G}} e^{-i(\omega t - \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{R}_\ell)} \mathbf{u}_\alpha(\mathbf{G})]$, where $\mathbf{R}_\ell =$

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Figure 1. Panel (a) displays the phonon band structure of the in-plane modes of a generic hexagonal lattice with broken inversion symmetry. The modes under consideration in this study are marked by red and blue arrows, with an accompanying illustration of sublattice movement. Panels (b) and (c) present the unfolded electronic band structure, both without and with e-ph coupling, taking into account replicas (0, 0), (1, 0), and (0, 1). The minor gap observed at each replica's Dirac point is due to a staggering potential. Parameters include: $\hbar\omega = 0.5\gamma_0$, $\gamma_1 = 0.001\gamma_0$, and $\Delta = 0.001\gamma_0$. The details of the phonon dispersion and the phonon modes can be found in Supporting Information.

$\ell_1 \mathbf{a}_1 + \ell_2 \mathbf{a}_2$ is the lattice vector of the corresponding unit cell labeled by $\ell = (\ell_1, \ell_2)$ and \mathbf{a}_j are the lattice vectors. $A_{\mathbf{G}}$ is a complex coefficient and $\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}(\mathbf{G})$ is the eigenvector of the phonon mode with momentum \mathbf{G} on sublattice $\alpha = \{A, B\}$. To make contact with the more compact notation of Eq. (1), we note that site n is defined by the unit cell and sublattice, defined by ℓ and α , respectively. The coupling between the electrons and the lattice vibrations is incorporated as a renormalization of the hopping amplitude between sites n and m , which takes into account the distance between them as follows [32, 33]:

$$\gamma_{n,m} = \gamma_0 \exp \left[-b \left(\frac{|\mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{r}_m|}{a_0} - 1 \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

where γ_0 is the hopping in the absence of distortions produced by the lattice vibrations ($\gamma_0 \simeq 2.7$ eV for graphene), b is a positive constant, a_0 the distance between nearest neighbors and $\mathbf{r}_n = \mathbf{r}_n^0 + \delta \mathbf{r}_n(t)$, with \mathbf{r}_n^0 the equilibrium position of site n . Considering small displacements from the equilibrium positions ($|\delta \mathbf{r}_n| \ll a_0$), the resulting Hamiltonian is given by:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_e + \sum_k \mathcal{H}_{\text{ph}}(\mathbf{G}_k) + \sum_k \mathcal{H}_{e\text{-ph}}(\mathbf{G}_k). \quad (3)$$

The phonon contribution for each mode can be written as $\mathcal{H}_{\text{ph}}(\mathbf{G}_k) = \hbar\omega_k a_k^\dagger a_k$, with a_k the annihilation operator of phonon with momentum \mathbf{G}_k and angular frequency ω_k . In our analysis we restrict the sum over k to only two zone boundary modes related to each other by time-reversal symmetry, with momenta \mathbf{G}^+ and \mathbf{G}^- , associated to valleys \mathbf{K}^+ and \mathbf{K}^- , respectively, and with the same angular frequency ω . Phonon modes outside high-symmetry points have wavelengths mismatched with the lattice, unlike those at these points which cause effects like phonon softening and Kohn anomalies. In our study, modes away from \mathbf{G}^+ and \mathbf{G}^- cannot connect states across valleys to open a gap. In this light, we consider the two high-symmetry modes non-perturbatively, while the remaining modes should remain perturbative [22, 34], thereby lessening their importance.

The electron phonon interaction term takes the form [28]:

$$\mathcal{H}_{e\text{-ph}}(\mathbf{G}_k) = -\gamma_1 \sum_{\langle n,m \rangle} c_n^\dagger c_m \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{n,m} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v}_m) a_k^\dagger + \text{h.c.}, \quad (4)$$

with $\mathbf{v}_n = e^{i\mathbf{G}_k \cdot \mathbf{R}_n} \mathbf{u}_\nu$, $\gamma_1 \ll \gamma_0$ the e-ph interaction strength, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{n,m} = (\mathbf{r}_n^0 - \mathbf{r}_m^0)/a_0$, and $\nu = \{A, B\}$ the sublattice of site n . The phonon modes considered present a circular (chiral) motion of the atoms at each sublattice, and is encoded in \mathbf{u}_ν , which is an intra-cell contribution to the chirality [8], and in the phase $e^{i\mathbf{G}_k \cdot \mathbf{R}_n}$ acquired by the motion in the different unit cells [8], the latter can be regarded as an inter-cell contribution.

To solve this problem we use the non-adiabatic and non-perturbative scheme introduced in Refs. [35, 36]. By writing the Hamiltonian in a Fock space basis for the electrons and phonons, we are left with a single particle problem in a higher dimensional space, where one additional dimension is added by each phonon mode. This can be appreciated by using the basis $\{|k, n_1, n_2\rangle = |k\rangle \otimes |n_1\rangle \otimes |n_2\rangle\}$, where $|k, n_1, n_2\rangle$ is the vibron state with an electron with wavevector k , n_1 phonons for the mode at \mathbf{G}^+ , and n_2 phonons for that at \mathbf{G}^- , see Fig. 1(a). Thus, in this picture, each electronic state has a series of 'replicas' associated with the phonon degrees of freedom. The unperturbed dispersion relations for each replica are shifted in energy by $(n_1 + n_2)\hbar\omega$. This is shown in Fig. 1(b), where the interaction is turned off.

Turning on the e-ph interaction leads to prominent modifications around $\varepsilon = \hbar\omega/2$ [see Fig. 1(c)]. The mode \mathbf{G}^+ enables (non-vertical) electronic transitions between $\mathbf{k} \simeq \mathbf{K}^-$ in the $(n_1, n_2) = (0, 0)$ replica and $\mathbf{k} \simeq \mathbf{K}^+$ in the $(1, 0)$ replica. In turn, the mode \mathbf{G}^- has a negligible effect there but couples the states with $\mathbf{k} \simeq \mathbf{K}^+$ in the $(0, 0)$ replica with those at $\mathbf{k} \simeq \mathbf{K}^-$ in the $(0, 1)$ replica. As a result of the superposition of these two effects, the $(n_1, n_2) = (0, 0)$ replica is fully gapped at $\hbar\omega/2$, while the $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$ replicas are only gapped around the \mathbf{K}^+ and \mathbf{K}^- valleys, respectively.

Figure 2. Local density of states ρ , shown in logarithmic scale $\log(1 + \rho)$. Panel (a) corresponds to the LDoS calculated for a semi-infinite slab in the vicinity of the top zigzag edge. Panel (b) shows the LDoS for a semi-infinite slab extending to the top, in the vicinity of the bottom zigzag edge. Panel (c) shows the LDoS in the vicinity of the center of an infinite system. The color scale shows the weight on the $(0, 0)$ replica. The parameters are: $\gamma_1 = 0.025 \gamma_0$, $\hbar\omega = 0.3 \gamma_0$, and $\Delta = 0.02 \gamma_0$.

In the limit of $\hbar\omega \ll \gamma_0$, the gap produced by G^+ in the $(0, 0)$ replica is given by [28] (a similar expression holds for G^-): $3\sqrt{2}\gamma_1 |\mathbf{L}^\dagger \mathbf{u}_A + \mathbf{R}^\dagger \mathbf{u}_B|$, where $\mathbf{L} = (1, -i)^T / \sqrt{2}$ ($\mathbf{R} = (1, i)^T / \sqrt{2}$) represents the counter-clockwise (clockwise) circular motion of the atoms and therefore encodes the chirality of the motion on each sublattice. Interestingly, here we find that the gap remains even when inversion symmetry in our generic model is preserved (we refer to the Supporting Information for more details). From the expression for the gap we can rationalize this by noting that although there is a sensitivity to the chiral motion on each sublattice, the contributions sum up so that there is no need of a nonvanishing phonon pseudoangular momentum. This expands the possibility of observing this phenomenon to a broader set of materials.

Let us now turn to the case of graphene ribbons. Since each mode acts selectively on a given valley, its effect is that described in [28]: it generates two copropagating edge states developing at the gapped valley, one at each opposite edge. This occurs for zigzag or zigzag-like geometries, where the edges do not introduce inter-valley processes. In our case, the concurrence of these two effects leads to a set of counterpropagating states at each edge of the sample, with an interesting feature: the propagation direction is linked to the phonon mode leading to their existence. Fig. 2 illustrates the local density of states ρ for the case of a wide zigzag ribbon. As the embedded schemes indicate, each panel evaluates ρ in different regions of the nanoribbon, thus indicating the localization of the edge states along the sample.

The origin of the edge states is related to the hybridization between the flat bands of the replicas. As we discussed above, these are superposition states with a contribution from the $(0, 0)$ replica and the other contribution from either replica $(1, 0)$ or $(0, 1)$, but never the two at the same time. It is im-

portant to note that, for a given edge of the ribbon, the phonon mode in which the state is hybridized establishes its direction of propagation. Considering one of the borders of the sample, the two localized edge states have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_{\leftarrow}\rangle &= C_{\leftarrow}^{(0,0)} |k^-, 0, 0\rangle + C_{\leftarrow}^{(1,0)} |k^+, 1, 0\rangle, \\ |\Psi_{\rightarrow}\rangle &= C_{\rightarrow}^{(0,0)} |k^+, 0, 0\rangle + C_{\rightarrow}^{(0,1)} |k^-, 0, 1\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where k^\pm is a wavevector around the \mathbf{K}^\pm valley. Eq. (5) shows the most important feature of the e-ph induced edge states: *the component complementary to that in $(0, 0)$ has a peculiar locking between electron valley, propagation direction and phonon mode*. In the following we will argue on how to exploit this property for the generation of entangled states and elaborate on a simulated experiment where this entanglement could be probed.

Peculiar entangled states.— As highlighted in [30], the generation of entangled states naturally occurs in solid state physics due to the inherent interaction tendencies. However, extracting these states in a practical manner remains challenging as one needs to separate the entangled parts. Conversely, in optics, the splitting of entangled parts can be readily facilitated by a beam splitter [31], while the process of entangling the states becomes the obstacle.

As the edge states of Eq. (5) present a locking between the propagation direction, the valley and the phonon mode involved, it is natural to think about how to exploit their entanglement. We propose a simple setup showed in Fig. 3(a) that simultaneously accomplishes the task of beam splitter and entangler. In the absence of excited phonons in the system (which is the usual expectation since the phonon energy is considerably smaller than $k_B T$), the system presents a bulk gap. Injecting charge into a zigzag edge under such conditions naturally separates the current while also entangling the

Figure 3. Panel (a): scheme of a setup where injecting charge to a zigzag ribbon could lead to entangled electron-phonon states, which are split in two different directions of propagation, each one being hybridized mainly with one of the two phonon modes related by time-reversal symmetry. This T-shaped configuration therefore works as a combined entangler and splitter. (b) Scheme of the interferometric setup used in our simulations to probe the entanglement of the states generated in the T-shaped area when the electrons enter the hexagon from the top. Partial or complete absence of interference in the bottom lead (shaded grey) is a hallmark of the entanglement. Panel (c) visualizes the phonon-polarized scattering wavefunction across different replicas ((0,0) in the top panel, (1,0) in the center and (0,1) in the bottom), demonstrating a preference for direction and thus revealing a polarization in the phonon state. The incoming electronic energy in these panels is taken $\varepsilon = 0.5\hbar\omega$. (d) and (e) show the total transmission probability for the hexagonal shape device with and without electron-phonon coupling at different energies. This is examined at energies where edge states are absent ($\varepsilon = 1.1\hbar\omega$ in (d) panel) and present ($\varepsilon = 0.5\hbar\omega$ in (e) panel). The x -axis is normalized by an area $A_o = \pi\tilde{r}^2$, where \tilde{r} is the effective radius of a circle enclosing the hexagonal device ($\tilde{r} = 1350a_0$). The transmission is normalized to the maximum value within the range depicted in the figure and the parameters are $\hbar\omega = 0.3\gamma_0$, $\gamma_1 = 0.05\gamma_0$, and $\Delta = 0.01\gamma_0$.

propagation direction with the valley and marker state. The ensuing state takes the following form:

$$|\Psi\rangle = C_{\leftarrow} |\Psi_{\leftarrow}\rangle + C_{\rightarrow} |\Psi_{\rightarrow}\rangle = |\phi\rangle \otimes |0,0\rangle + |\xi\rangle, \quad (6)$$

where

$$|\xi\rangle = B_{\leftarrow} |k^+, 1, 0\rangle + B_{\rightarrow} |k^-, 0, 1\rangle, \quad (7)$$

is a maximally entangled e-ph state, with the phononic state playing the role of a *which path* marker. In other terms, in the setup of Fig. 3(a) the incoming electrons are placed into the state described by Eqs. (6) and (7), and the two terms composing the maximally entangled part [Eq. (7)] get separated (*split*) as the wave-packet propagates.

One of the prevailing challenges is identifying evidence of quantum entanglement. For this purpose, we turn our attention to a simulated interferometric configuration where the presence of entanglement implies the absence of interference, often referred to as the “which path” interferometer [37]. This inference is rooted on the fact that the counterpropagating components across distinct marker states cannot interfere, given their orthogonality [38].

We can scrutinize the suppression of interference in our simulation by modulating the energy of incident electrons in a ‘ring’ geometry threaded by a magnetic flux. The key differences are expected to materialize in the emergence (or non-emergence) of e-ph polarized edge states. Subsequently, we will use the visibility of the interference pattern, derived from the ratio of the Aharonov-Bohm oscillations’ amplitude to the transmission peak, as an expected evidence of entanglement.

Interference patterns as a witness of entanglement.— We build the interferometric setup using the Kwant package [39]. The system is illustrated in Fig. 3(b) and the details of the setup are presented in the Supporting Information. In this configuration, a magnetic field perpendicular to the plane threads the device, inducing Aharonov-Bohm oscillations in the conductance. The probability associated with the scattering wavefunction is depicted in Fig. 3(c), confirming that propagation occurs with negligible backscattering and the locking between the dominant phonon mode and the propagation direction.

Fig. 3(d,e) show the transmission probability for an incoming electronic energy inside the gap ($\varepsilon = 0.5\hbar\omega$) and also well above it ($\varepsilon = 1.1\hbar\omega$). Our goal is to visualize whether a suppression of interference is evident or not. To better serve this purpose, since the number of propagating channels is much

higher outside the gap, we normalize the transmitted signal by its peak value. Furthermore, we compare the numerics including (continuous line) and excluding electron-phonon interaction (dashed line). For energies outside the gap (panel (d)), both curves show a similar behavior due to the small hybridization between electrons and phonons. In contrast, for energies inside the gap, panel (e) shows a strong suppression of interference when the electron-phonon interaction is turned on: The visibility of the oscillations is reduced by an order of magnitude in the system with e-ph, 0.015, compared to 0.085 without e-ph coupling. The suppression of the interference can also be extracted from the Fourier transform of this signal (Supplementary Information) and it offers evidence of the entanglement of the electron-phonon states generated in the system.

Final remarks.— A possible experimental ground for this physics is graphene, or graphene on hBN [40, 41] which shows enhanced mobility [42]. Based on the analytic expression for the gap, one can see that e-ph interaction strengths of $\gamma_1 = 0.0002\gamma_0 - 0.002\gamma_0 = 0.54 - 5.4$ meV generate a gap in the range of 4.6 – 46 meV which would need low to moderate cryogenic temperatures (more details in the Supporting Information). Furthermore, transport experiments could be helped by scanning gate microscopy [43] and the use of angle resolved photo-emission spectroscopy (ARPES) to reveal the gap formation.

Our study reveals how electron-phonon interaction with zone-boundary modes facilitate the formation of a gap, with counter-propagating edge states manifesting a unique locking between propagation direction, valley, and excited phonon mode. This adds to our understanding of electron-phonon interactions and their entanglement in solid state physics. We also propose an experiment that confirms this entanglement through the observed suppression of interference in an interferometric setup. As a byproduct, we also show a case where the circular motion of the atoms on each sublattice produce effects which do not require inversion symmetry breaking (or a non-vanishing phonon pseudoangular momentum). This illuminates the role of phonons in creating unconventional hybrid electron-phonon states, and suggests potential avenues for exploiting these states in future research.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: XXXX
This file includes a discussion on the phonon modes and how they are computed, a brief discussion on the gap, also with simulations for the case of graphene and also more details on the calculations for the interferometric setup.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the support of Fondecyt (Chile) under grant number 1211038, and by the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 873028 (HYDROTRONICS Project). L. E. F. F. T. also acknowledges the support of The Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics and the Simons Foundation. H. L. C. is member of CONICET and acknowledges financial support by SECYT-UNC and ANPCyT (PICT-2018-03587). J.M. is supported by Fondecyt (Chile) under grant number 3200697 and Fondecyt regular number 1230747.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

LEFFT and HLC discussed an initial idea for the project. JM carried most of the numerics and prepared an initial draft. HLC carried some of the numerics that was crossed checked with those produced by JM. All authors discussed the results and agreed on the main points of the draft.

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Figure 4. *
TOC Graphic